

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH COLORATIVE COMPONENTS IN RUSSIAN, ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LINGUISTIC WORLDVIEWS

Kuanishbay Djumamuratov

PhD student, KarSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18185913>

Annotatsiya: *Tadqiqotda rus, ingliz va qoraqalpoq tillaridagi rang komponentli frazeologizmlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Asarning ahamiyati turli til oilalariga mansub tillarni qiyosiy tadqiq qilish va etnik guruhlarining madaniy o'ziga xosligini eng yorqin ifodalovchi xususiyatlar bo'lgan frazeologizmlarni tahlil qilishga bog'liq. Frazeologik birliklarni chuqur tahlil qilish fanning o'ziga xosligini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotda frazeologik ekvivalentlik muammosini tahlil qilish uning nazariy ahamiyatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqotning ikkita asosiy usuli - leksikografik tahlil usuli va qiyosiy yondashuv.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ekvivalentlik, ramziylik, baholovchilik, frazeologik birliklar, kolorativ komponentlar, oq, qora, sariq va qizil.*

Abstract: *The study looks at phraseologisms with a colorative component in the Russian, English, and Karakalpak languages. The work's importance depends on its comparative research of languages from different language families and its analysis of phraseologisms, which are the features that most vividly convey the cultural distinctiveness of ethnic groups. The thorough analysis of phraseological units illustrates the uniqueness of the science. The study's analysis of the phraseological equivalency problem contributes to its theoretical significance. The two primary research approaches are the lexicographic analysis method and the comparative approach.*

Keywords: *equivalence, symbolism, evaluativeness, phraseological units, colorative components, white, black, yellow and red.*

One of the elements of the environment that affects a person is colour. The most crucial aspect of the visual perception process is the qualities of colour. Designating colours is a means of expressing oneself. Nine primary purposes of colour have been identified by scientists; the most significant of them, in our opinion, are aesthetic, expressive, communicative, and identifying. The study's focus was on phraseological units in the English, Karakalpak, and Russian languages that have a colorative component.

The outcomes of an individual's perception of the outside world throughout their life are documented in what is known as their "world picture." The word was first used in the 19th and 20th centuries in relation to the physical image of the world by G. Hertz and M. The Planck. Its emergence in the field of linguistics was made possible by the scientific publications of L. Weisgerber. Anthropologist Robert Redfield interprets this phenomena as a worldview typical of a certain ethnic group; it is a particular, subjective view of oneself, one's actions, life, and the world. "A specific image of the world that is never its mirror image" is what is meant by "a picture of the world." [5, page 60].

Since ethnic realities directly affect language and its semantics, language is the most essential means of forming and preserving information. Language reflects an individual's vision

of the world and himself. For this reason, reality as reflected in language is not the same as reality itself. A linguistic picture of the world is described as the entirety of concepts that humanity has learned about it from both reality and daily activities taken together and expressed in language. This phrase was first used by V. von Humboldt, whose theory of a unique worldview emerged in the early nineteenth century within the context of classical German philosophy.

Prominent linguists including F. Schlegel, A.A. Potebnya, E. Sepir, and B.L. Wharf studied the world's vocabulary. Among the Russian scholars, F.F. Fortunatov, N.D. Arutyunova, and Yu.N. Karaulov deserve special mention.

The multitude of interpretations of this linguistic phenomenon raises many questions for linguists. Definitions cannot become widely accepted because scientists tracking the linguistic picture of the world concentrate on specific aspects of the concept; nonetheless, the multitude of interpretations is reduced to a narrow and broad understanding of the phenomenon:

1. The subjective view of the objective world through the lens of language use is known as the linguistic picture of the world.

2. The worldview expressed in language is regarded as a type of fixed scheme of reality perception.

Thus, linguist V.A. Maslova assumed that the linguistic picture of the world is a formative link of human self- and world perception, establishing social norms of behaviour and reflecting the perception of the outside world: "communicational behaviour, understanding of the outside world, and an individual's inner world are all determined by the linguistic picture of the world." It captures the manner of speech and thought typical of a specific era, complete with its national, cultural, and spiritual values." [3, page 65]

Since phraseological units frequently reflect the national character of a language, the phraseological picture of the world is an essential component of the linguistic picture of the world. Replicable phrases with a comprehensive meaning are known as phraseological units. "The phraseological fund of the language is a valuable source of information about the culture and mentality of the people, in which the people's ideas about myths, customs, rituals, habits, morals, behaviour are preserved." [3, page 4] As a result, phraseological units secondary reflect the worldview of the entire population, their social structure, and their ideology rather than that of specific people or social groups.

Under the influence of Sh. Bali, phraseology emerged as a separate field of lexicology, and V.V. Vinogradov laid the groundwork for the development of phraseology in Russia. From the perspective of semantic fusion of components, linguists categorise phraseological units into three groups: combinations, unities, and merges. The classification was broadened by researcher N.M. Shansky, who included phraseological expressions as a new category. A.V. Kunin, V.N. Telia, and D.N. Shmelev are just a few of the scientists who have published recent research highlighting phraseological issues from the perspectives of semantics, morphology, and syntax. However, the fact that various researchers interpret the same concepts differently and that there is ambiguity in the terminology raises a lot of questions about phraseology as a field.

Any ethnic group's quirks and national mindset are best captured by the phraseological system. Thus, phraseological units are frequently used to designate signs, objects, attributes, and processes. We study phraseological units with a colorative component in our scientific work. Each ethnic group's cultural tradition has established correlations between its unique colour meanings and the universality of colour perception among society's members.

The classification of B. Berlin and P. Kay is well known. After studying 78 languages, they concluded that 11 fundamental colours started to be encoded in any language's history in a fixed order, and that the stages at which terms first appeared corresponded to the stages at which languages evolved linguistically. [7, page 11]

There has been some research on phraseological units with colour meanings in individual languages, like Japanese, German, and French, but not enough in multiple languages. The study looks at phraseological units in English, Russian, and Karakalpak that have colour components that, in R.M. Frumkina's classification, fall into the main colours. This means that these units' interpretations are linked to objects that typically possess the following colour: black, red, blue, green, yellow, and white. We also draw attention to the colour blue separately. The classification of Y. Solodub [2], which identifies the following categories of interlanguage equivalents and analogues that provide challenges in inter language and intercultural communication, will serve as the foundation for this paper:

1. Absolute equivalents in Russian, English and Karakalpak with the same imagery, semantics, and structure.

2. Partial equivalents with distinct structure or constituents but same semantics and internal form.

3. Phonological units that are non-equivalent and lack counterparts in other languages. These are colloquialisms specific to a particular ethnic group that are primarily connected to a particular language.

4. Precise phraseological units derived from exact translations between languages. The most popular are literal translations of biblical and mythological phraseological units.

We were able to arrive at certain conclusions through the analysis of semantic groups of phraseological units with a colorative component. These conclusions are shown in the suggested tables.

Phraseological units with a color component in English:

Color	Symbolism		
	Religion	Personality	Financial situation
Black	Grief, death <i>blacks guards</i> / <i>mutes at a funeral</i>	Despondency, hopelessness <i>Black looks/ evil looks</i>	Wealth <i>Black diamonds / black coal; Black dog/ small tin coin</i>
Blue	Eternity/immortality, joy <i>blue monday / last Monday before Lent</i>	Refinement, cruelty <i>true blue / a real aristocrat;</i> <i>Blue beard/ cruel tyrant</i>	Wealth <i>Blue books/ lists of government officials</i>
Green	Paradise Gardens, resurrection <i>green thursday / Maundy Thursday</i>	Immaturity, youth, envy <i>Greenstick fracture/ fracture in young people;</i> <i>green glasses/ envy of other people's success</i>	Low quality, cheapness <i>Green labour / clothes made from cheap low quality fabric qualities</i>

Red	Torment, resurrection <i>Red boo/ torture</i>	Embarrassment, shame, immorality to get / have a red face/ blush; red-handed/ caught in the act	Gold, money <i>A red kettle / gold watch; red book of the exchequer / English income book monarch</i>
Yellow	Patronage <i>the yellow hammer/a bird whose eggs have Red spots</i>	Jealousy, envy, fear <i>yellow-bellies / frogs</i>	Money, wealth <i>yellow fever/yellow fever; yellow stuff/ gold, money</i>
White	Cleansing from sins	Purity	Wealth, silver
	<i>White bird / conscience or the soul of a person; White caps/ Followers of Prophet Muhammad</i>	<i>white / Plays with "white"; White witch / cunning, Proficient in art of white magic</i>	<i>White tincture/ White elixir, capable of Transforming any metal in Silver</i>

Phraseological units with a color component in Russian:

Color	Symbolism		
	Religion	Personality	Financial situation
Black	Unclean forces, death <i>Черная книга/ The book of spells</i>	Cunning, evil, sullenness <i>черная душа / a treacherous person; Чернее ночи / very gloomy</i>	Low financial position <i>черный народ / peasants; Черный день / difficult time in life</i>
Blue	Happiness, joy <i>синяя птица / symbol of happiness</i>	Rudeness, masculinity <i>синий чулок / woman absorbed in science</i>	-
Green	-	Youth, youth <i>Зеленый юнец / inexperienced due to youth</i>	-
Red	-	External beauty, shame <i>красная девица/ beautiful girl; Красный как мак/ Blushing with embarrassment</i>	Wealth <i>Красные дни / good luck time Красная цена / goods at a favorable price</i>
Yellow	-	Naivety <i>желторотый птенец / young naive man</i>	Cheapness <i>желтенькая бумажка / ruble credit card</i>

White	Holliness, purity, divine <i>белый свет / The world</i>	Lies, rudeness <i>Шито белыми нитками/ Clumsily hidden; Сказка про белого бычка/ blatant lie</i>	Poor financial situation <i>дела как сажка бела / joking badly No good</i>
--------------	---	--	--

Phraseological units with a color component in the Karakalpak language:

Color	Symbolism		
	Religion	Personality	Financial situation
Black	Unclean forces, death, curse <i>Black magic</i>	Evil, sullenness, negativity, failure <i>Kewli qara, Baxıtı qara Qara kúsh, Qara qayǵı, Qara mańlay, Qara niyet</i>	Poor financial situation <i>Qara taban / peasant Qara kún / difficult time in life</i>
Blue		Happiness <i>Bası kókke jetiw, jeri kókke siymadı / to feel very happy</i>	The sky <i>Kúli kókke suwirıldı (ushti) / to be destroyed</i>
Red		beauty, woman/girl, shame <i>Qızıl kóylek / beautiful nature; Qızıl shúberek / woman, girl Beti qızardı / Blushing with shame</i>	Wealth <i>Qızıl valyuta / доллар денег</i>
Yellow	Fire of hell	Youth, sadness <i>Awzınan (awzınıń) sarısı ketpegen / too young; Sari uwayım / concern</i>	Pregnant female cow <i>Sarpayın sarǵaytıw / Jelinin sarǵaytıw</i>
White	Holliness, purity, divine white color / The world	The truth, purity, generosity <i>Aq degeni – aq, qara degeni – qara / (white – truth, black –lie), Aq degeni - alǵıs, qara degeni - qarǵıs (white – applause (honor), black – curse), Aq pátiya aldı – (honored) - Súttan aq, suwdan taza (whiter than milk, purer than water); Aq kewil (generous)</i>	Cotton, poor condition <i>Aq altın / cotton Aq perdesi shıǵıw / become poor</i>

Within the framework of the color meanings included in the phraseological units, there is a similarity between the Russian, English and Karakalpak languages in the number of coloratives. The analyzed phraseological units coincide in structural and grammatical models and types of meaning, which indicates the kinship of the linguocreative thinking of native speakers of these languages. The subject of special attention was non-equivalent phraseological units with a colorative component. Dominant colors were identified for each linguistic culture.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. КУНИН, А.В. Англо-русский фразеологический словарь. Москва: Русский язык, 1999. 512 с. ISBN 5-87-905-042-4.

2. ЛЕОНТЬЕВ, А.А. Языковое сознание и образ мира. Язык и сознание: парадоксальная рациональность. В: Сборник научных статей. Москва: Институт языкознания РАН, 1993. с. 16-21.
3. МАСЛОВА, В.А. Лингвокультурология. Учебное пособие для студентов высших учебных заведений. Москва: Академия, 2001. 208с. ISBN5-76-95-0745-4
4. МОЛОТКОВ, А.И. Фразеологический словарь русского языка. Москва: Советская энциклопедия, 1968. 543 с.
5. СЕРЕБРЕННИКОВ, Б.А. Роль человеческого фактора в языке. Язык и картина мира. Москва: Наука, 1988. 212 с. ISBN 5-02-010878-2
6. ФРУМКИНА, Р.М. Психоллингвистика. Учебное пособие для студентов высших учебных заведений. Москва: Академия, 2001. 25 с. ISBN 978-5-4468-0305-7
7. BERLIN, V., KAYP. Basic Color Terms. Berkley: University of California Press, 1969. p. 390 ISBN 3-89706-159-7
8. FRANCIS, V., PARKINSON, D. Oxford Idioms Dictionary for Learners of English. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009. 509 p. ISBN 2-31478-739-7
9. www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=black-letter%20day
10. Paxratdinov Q., Q. Bekniyazov. Qaraqalpaq tilindegi frazeologizmler
11. J. Eshbaev, Qaraqalpaq tiliniń qısqasha frazeologiyalıq sózligi Nókis – 1985
12. Aynazarova G. Qaraqalpaq tilinde teńles eki komponentli frazeologizmler Monografiya. Nókis, 2005